

RESIDUAL PROPERTIES AND DAMAGE EVOLUTION OF FLAX-EPOXY COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO FATIGUE LOADING

F. Bensadoun^{1(*)}, K.A.M Vallons¹, L.B. Lessard², I. Verpoest¹, A.W. Van Vuure¹

¹ KU Leuven - Department of Materials Engineering, Kasteelpark Arenberg 44 - bus 2450, 3001 Heverlee, Belgium

² McGill University- Department of Mechanical Engineering, 817 Sherbrooke St. West, Montreal, Quebec, H3A0C3, Canada

**corresponding author: farida.bensadoun@mtm.kuleuven.be*

Keywords: flax, energy dissipation, fatigue, residual properties

ABSTRACT

Flax fibre-based composites have seen increased use in recent years and new questions have arisen concerning their longevity. Thus, it is necessary to assess the long term properties such as fatigue and damage development. The present study focuses on the characterization of the residual properties and damage development of flax-epoxy composites subjected to fatigue loading. Understanding these properties would allow easier prediction of long-term viability and durability of these materials and would as well facilitate their use. The fibre architecture was found to have a strong effect on the fatigue behaviour where higher strength and modulus composites have a postponed damage initiation, increased fatigue life, a reduced damage propagation rate as well as a higher energy dissipation due to high damage activity in the early stages. Residual properties were assessed on samples loaded for 500 000 cycles at 5Hz at a $S/S_0=0.3$ stress level. It was found that the decrease in properties was around 15% as compared to the static properties.

INTRODUCTION

Flax fibres based composite use in the composites industry has been exponentially increasing, thanks to the good acoustic and thermal insulation, enhanced vibration absorption, good mechanical properties as well as renewability. As of today, a major lack of data on flax fibre durability properties, such as post-fatigue behaviour, has been limiting the use of these materials in many applications. Very few papers relate the residual properties of fatigue tested composite, the damage accumulation mechanism as well as the post-fatigue properties. For composite materials, the residual properties like the stiffness and strength are directly related to the damage state [1, 2]. To monitor this build-up of damage, the cyclic hysteresis behaviour is used in order to evaluate the loss of stiffness, material energy dissipation and damage development [3, 4].

Throughout its lifetime, the composite will encounter certain damage that will affect its overall performance. Although fatigue loading does not instantly reduce the strength of the composite, it does have an effect on the stiffness. During fatigue testing, early damage causes a fast and steep decrease of the stiffness, which is followed by a stabilisation and slow degradation of the composite properties. Close to failure, heavily damaged zones develop, leading to a strong decrease in stiffness, and finally this will cause the material to break [5, 6]. In the case of natural fibres, Gassan et al.[7] and Bensadoun et al. [8] have found that composite with higher strength and modulus with an increased fibre-matrix

adhesion, caused a delayed damage initiation and reduced damage propagation which limits the loss in properties.

A gradual build-up of residual strain in the samples is often noticed during fatigue loading, especially in samples with none or only a limited amount of fibres in the testing direction [9-12]. In tensile-tensile fatigue cases, if the strain at minimum applied stress in each cycle is plotted versus the number of cycles, a steep increase is seen in the initial stages of the test, indicating a build-up of permanent or residual strain. After this, the increase of this strain becomes more moderate. The build-up of such residual strain during fatigue has been explained by the development of damage in the material, e.g. in [11, 12]. El Sawi et al. [12] have shown that there is a correlation between the residual strain increase and the matrix crack density in flax fibre reinforced epoxy manufactured with UD and $\pm 45^\circ$ cross ply laminates. The residual properties can be measured and compared to the pre-fatigue behaviour if fatigue testing stops before final failure. A study by Vallons et al. [11] has shown that for cross-ply carbon-epoxy composites, there is no influence of the fatigue loading on the post-fatigue properties when the loading was applied in the fibre directions. However in the bias direction, a decrease in strength and stiffness was found as well as a significant decrease in failure strain. Yuanjian et al. [13] have looked at the influence of fatigue loading on the quasi-static modulus of randomly oriented hemp and stitch bonded biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre composites at different stages of the fatigue process. They have found that for transverse tested samples, there was a steady decrease in modulus for the glass fibre composite, but no decrease was noted for the hemp fibre composite up to final failure.

During fatigue testing, the deformation and appearance of damage in the composite will dissipate a certain amount of energy with increasing cycling and only part of this energy is given back during unloading. This phenomenon will leave the specimen with a permanent strain that will accumulate through time [14, 15]. This will cause a shift of the hysteresis loop towards increasing strain levels [11]. Furthermore, in tension-tension fatigue loading, the composite dissipates most of the energy in the initial phase of cyclic loading displayed by a wide hysteresis loop [4, 9, 16]. These wider loops are related to greater energy dissipation at the fibre–matrix interface and the decrease in loop area in time and the small increase in steepness of the loading curve are consistent with stiffening of composites in the fibre direction as stated by Towo et al. [4]. Liang et al. [9] observed that the energy dissipation of unidirectional (UD) flax-epoxy composite and a (0,90) cross-ply composite exhibit a decrease in energy dissipation with increasing cycles.

In this study, nine flax-epoxy architecture configurations were subjected to tension-tension fatigue ($R=0.1$) at various stress levels. Their mechanical performance was assessed through tensile testing. Strain monitoring was used during testing in order to monitor the stiffness degradation and to register the hysteresis loops to investigate the energy dissipation capacity of each material as well as the permanent deformation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Nine configurations of flax fibre reinforced composites were produced with a thermoset epoxy matrix *Epikote 828LVEL*. For the cross-linking, the matrix is mixed with the hardener *Dytek DCH-99* at a 15.2 phr ratio. The 2 mm thick laminates are composed of several layers of fabrics in order to obtain a fibre volume fraction (V_f) of 30% for the random mat and of 40% for the other architectures. The different textiles used as well as the matrix are described in Table 1.

Flax fibre preform architectures	Mat	Plain weave	Twill			Quasi-UD* ¹	Unidirectional ¹
Areal density ρ_{sur} (g/m ²)	300	285	400	200	150	300	200
1 ply thickness (mm)	0.21	0.2	0.23	0.14	0.103	0.21	0.14
Acronym	Random Mat	Plain Weave	Low Twist Twill	Medium Twist Twill	High Twist Twill	Quasi-UD	UD
Matrix Type	Commercial Name	Modulus (GPa)		Strength (MPa)			
Epoxy (Thermoset)	Epikote 828 LEVEL	2.7		70			

* 90% of fibres in 0° direction and 10% in the 90° direction.

¹ Quasi-UD and UD laminate were made in both UD and symmetric cross-ply lay-up (0,90)_s

Table 1: Flax fibres and epoxy matrix characteristics.

2.2 Composite manufacturing and Testing

The composites were manufactured using the Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) technique. A spacer was used to adjust the depth of the cavity in order to obtain the thickness of 2 mm± 0.05mm. The experimental parameters were $P_{inlet}=+1bar$, $P_{vacuum}=-0.99bar$ and a consolidation pressure of 3 bars. The injection temperature was 40°C and the temperature was then increased to 70°C for 1h. The plates were then de-moulded and post-cured at 150°C for 1h. Tensile tests were performed using an Instron #4505 testing machine with samples of 2x25x250 mm, a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min, a load cell of 30 kN and a gauge length of 150 mm according to ASTM D3039 standard. A 50 mm gauge length extensometer with a 10 mm travel was used to monitor the strain. A minimum of 5 samples, previously end-tabbed to avoid stress concentration at the grips, were tested to ensure reproducibility and reliable standard deviations. The tensile stiffness is calculated in two distinct regions, E_1 between 0 and 0.1% strain and E_2 between 0.3 and 0.5 % strain. Two stiffness values are calculated because of a decrease in stiffness around 0.2% strain. The stiffness E_1 and E_2 and the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) obtained from the static test are presented in Figure 1. The UTS is used to determine the applied load level used during fatigue testing and all properties are later compared to the post-fatigue properties.

Tension–tension fatigue tests were carried out according to the ASTM D3479 standard on a MTS hydraulic fatigue testing device with a 100kN load cell. The loading ratio was set to $R= 0.1$ with a loading frequency of 5 Hz and load levels (S/S_0) were used ranging from 0.3 to 0.9 UTS. Tests were conducted at room temperature of 22°C. A tapered sine signal was used to gradually increase the load amplitude to avoid the overshoot of the load in the early cycles. The test is set to stop if the samples do not fail after 10^6 cycles, referred to as N_{max} . Hysteresis loops and stiffness degradation were captured continuously using a fatigue graded extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm. A minimum of 3-4 samples for each load level were tested.

a)

b)

Figure 1: a) the E1 and E2 moduli and b) the ultimate tensile strength for the investigated flax/epoxy composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cyclic creep and energy dissipation

Fatigue test results are shown in figures 2 and 3. For all investigated textile architectures, the hysteresis loops in each cycle are slightly shifted towards a higher strain, indicating a developing permanent deformation of the sample. It is seen that the hysteresis loops for the UD-composites show a smaller energy dissipation and a reduced shift to the right, compared to the random mat or the quasi-UD (0,90) composites. This indicates a lower permanent deformation and/or damage accumulation for the UD-composites. As the applied stress is 30% of the maximum stress and $R=0.1$, the cycling goes from a minimum stress in the linear elastic region of the static tensile stress strain curve to a maximum stress in the transition zone (after the yield point) shown in . Thus, the specimens are loaded into the visco-elasto-plastic region. This leads to a permanent deformation, which may be related to plastic deformation but not necessarily to damage. This permanent deformation can be seen in Figure 4 showing an increase of the strain at the minimum stress as a function of the number of cycles.

The creep-like behaviour for a loading ratio of 0.1, observed in this study was also found by Monte et al. [17]. As the permanent strain increases with increasing number of cycles, the minimum strain and stress levels for damage initiation are both reached, leading to the shift of the hysteresis loops to higher strain for a constant stress level [11]. Furthermore, the residual strain could also be a consequence of elastic deformation in the composite. The results also show that permanent deformation increases in a power law fashion with increasing number of cycles. Upon a closer look at the results from the permanent strain, the fastest permanent strain increase is observed for the plain weave and the low twist twill with a variation of 38% and 32% between cycle 1000 and cycle 500 000 at 30% of UTS.

Figure 2: Flax roving with binding polyester yarn in the low twist twill textile.

Taking a closer look at the post fatigue properties, it is observed that the low twist twill, which shows the highest permanent strain, encounters the strongest decrease in both stiffness and strength, as reported in the previous sections. This may be due to the physical shape of the yarns that are wrapped around a unidirectional bundle of fibre, which causes a misalignment of the fibres and thus a decrease in properties. These binding yarns (see Figure 2) create stress concentration points which increase the chance of damage coupled to the shear-induced damage between the fibres and the matrix, leading to an increase in the permanent deformation of the sample. As seen in the results obtained and presented in Figure 4, the introduction of a misalignment has equivalent impact on the residual properties and permanent strain, as the presence of a combination of high twist and crimp.

Figure 3: Position of the transition region in a static tensile test.

Figure 4 : Plastic deformation through cycling. Display of the minimum attained strain level during fatigue cycling displaying the elongation of the sample during the test at a stress level of $S/S_0=0.3$.

During the fatigue testing, the deformation and creation of damage in flax/epoxy specimens will dissipate a certain amount of energy during the increasing load phase, and only part of this energy is given back during unloading. This phenomenon will leave the specimen with a permanent strain that will accumulate through time and affect the overall mechanical properties (reduction of the stiffness) of the composites as well as further damage propagation [15].

The shift of the hysteresis loop as seen in Figure 5 towards increasing strain levels is an indication of permanent deformation of the specimen. Additionally, a larger stress-strain (σ - ϵ) hysteresis loop area and a slight increase of the slope in the early cycles compared to cycles close to the failure of the sample was observed for four of the nine architectures. When the loops get slimmer, this is a sign that no more damage is created, i.e. the number of matrix cracks reaches a saturation state [11].

Figure 5: Stress-strain data from fatigue testing random mat – epoxy composite at $S/S_0=0.3$.

Figure 4 shows data for energy dissipation throughout the fatigue testing. Similarly to cyclic creep, a three stages evolution is observed for all configurations, with a first rapid increase in energy dissipation (Region I) due the appearance of internal damage followed by a short stable region between cycle 5000 and 10 000 (Region II) and a gradual decrease in energy dissipation when the damage saturation has occurred, which is starting in between 10 000 and 50 000 cycles up to the end of the test. The random mat encountered the highest increase in energy dissipation with an increase of 25% between cycle 1000 and cycle 5000 as seen in Figure 6. The same behaviour is observed for all architectures. However, for the UD composites, no Region II is observed and a stable decrease from cycle 1000 in energy dissipation is observed. It has to be noted that the UD composites are the ones which had the highest energy dissipation in the early cycles (<1000 cycles).

Figure 6: Evolution of energy dissipation for all studied flax-epoxy composites at 30% UTS.

Post-fatigue properties

Following 1/2 million cycles, samples from each architecture were tested in static tension to determine their residual properties. The moduli E_1 and E_2 , and the ultimate tensile strength were determined and are presented in figure 5. The post-fatigue tensile tests show that the fatigue-tested samples exhibit similar properties to the static-tested samples with no significant decrease in mechanical properties. The same behaviour was observed with hemp fibre based composites [18]. Only the low twist twill displays a strong decrease of 20% for both E_1 , E_2 and the tensile strength. For the remaining configurations, tensile values comparable to the pre-fatigue values were found. It is hypothesised the damage that is formed during fatigue likely postpones the formation of new damage during the post-fatigue tensile tests [11, 19].

Taking a closer look at the results, a moderate increase of the E_1 modulus is observed for the Quasi-UD (0,90) by +5%, the UD (0,90) with 10% , whereas the E_1 -modulus for the quasi-UD (+ 0.5%) and UD composites (+ 2.5%) remain almost constant. A different behaviour is observed for their E_2 modulus with stable behaviour (UD (0,90)) or an increased modulus up to 25% for the Quasi-UD (0,90). For the previous laminates, all the strength values decrease compared to the static value, besides the UD (0,90) being the most stable composite configuration. In the case of the plain weave, the E_1 remains stable while the E_2 increases by 13% while for the high twist twill the E_1 increases by 8%, but the E_2 decreases by 10%. For both these architectures, the yarns are wet spun which causes the water to dissolve pectin which leads to their partial fibrillation. This phenomenon allows a better impregnation within the yarns and its technical fibres, increasing the fibre-matrix interface and its load bearing efficiency. The mechanical properties increase as the aspect ratio increases; elementary fibres tend to have a higher aspect ratio than technical fibres and the effective area in contact with the matrix increases [20]. Hence, for composites containing wet spun yarns, an enhanced fatigue performance leading to lower degradation through time and an increased post-fatigue stiffness are reported in this study.

a)

b)

Figure 7: Post-fatigue properties of flax-epoxy composites, a) the tensile modulus E1 and E2 and b) the tensile strength.

CONCLUSIONS

Tension-Tension fatigue tests were carried out in order to assess the long-term behaviour of flax/epoxy composites. The main conclusions are:

- The permanent strain has been found to be limited at low loading levels, and is affected by either plastic deformation of the composite or the appearance of damage or a combination of both. Also, most of permanent strain build-up happens in the early cycles.
- The post-fatigue properties were found to be comparable to the initial static test results except for the low twist twill which had a stronger decrease in properties due to the presence of the binding yarns that act as stress concentrators.
- The flax composites with higher strength and modulus also show a delayed damage initiation and a reduced damage propagation rate. This was illustrated by the limited hysteresis (smaller loop area) and their low strain shift, presenting low plastic deformation and/or damage accumulation.
- All flax-epoxy composites have shown a larger energy dissipation in the early cycles as shown by the analysis of hysteresis loops in tension–tension.

Overall, the behaviour of flax-epoxy composites is comparable to the behaviour glass fibre reinforced composites related in literature and thus suitable for many new or existing industrial applications. Further optimisation of composite lay-up and combination with suitable matrices, need to be made. One of the targets would be to increase the fibre/matrix interface bonding, which may increase the mechanical and the fatigue properties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is sponsored by the Fonds Du Québec– Recherche Nature et Technologies (FQRNT) and the European Flax and Hemp Confederation (CELC) as well as the European Biobuild Project FP7 285689. Special Thanks to Bart Pelgrims for his valuable insight and advice on fatigue testing.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. M. Daniel and A. Charewicz, "Fatigue damage mechanisms and residual properties of graphite/epoxy laminates," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 25, pp. 793-808, 1986.
- [2] R. Talreja, *Fatigue of composite materials*: Technomic, 1987.
- [3] C. L. Hacker and M. P. Ansell, "Fatigue damage and hysteresis in wood-epoxy laminates," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 36, pp. 609-621, 2001/02/01 2001.
- [4] A. N. Towo and M. P. Ansell, "Fatigue of sisal fibre reinforced composites: constant-life diagrams and hysteresis loop capture," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 68, pp. 915-924, 2008.
- [5] W. Van Paeppegem and J. Degrieck, "A new coupled approach of residual stiffness and strength for fatigue of fibre-reinforced composites," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 24, pp. 747-762, 2002.
- [6] M. M. Shokrieh and L. B. Lessard, "Multiaxial fatigue behaviour of unidirectional plies based on uniaxial fatigue experiments—II. Experimental evaluation," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 19, pp. 209-217, 1997.
- [7] J. Gassan, "A study of fibre and interface parameters affecting the fatigue behaviour of natural fibre composites," *Composites - Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 33, pp. 369-374, 2002.
- [8] F. Bensadoun, J. Baets, A.W. Van Vuure, and I. Verpoest, "Fatigue behaviour of flax reinforced composites," presented at the ECCM16 - 16th European Conference On Composite Materials, Seville, Spain, 2014.
- [9] S. Liang, P.-B. Gning, and L. Guillaumat, "Properties evolution of flax/epoxy composites under fatigue loading," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 63, pp. 36-45, 2014.
- [10] S. Liang, P. B. Gning, and L. Guillaumat, "A comparative study of fatigue behaviour of flax/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 72, pp. 535-543, 2012.
- [11] K. Vallons, M. Zong, V. Lomov, and I. Verpoest, "Carbon composites based on multi-axial multi-ply stitched preforms - Part 6. Fatigue behaviour at low loads: Stiffness degradation and damage development," *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 38, pp. 1633-1645, 2007.
- [12] I. E. Sawi, Z. Fawaz, and R. Zitoune, "An investigation of the damage mechanisms and fatigue life diagrams of flax fiber-reinforced polymer laminates," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 49, pp. 2338–2346, 2014.
- [13] T. Yuanjian and D. H. Isaac, "Impact and fatigue behaviour of hemp fibre composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 67, pp. 3300-3307, 2007.
- [14] C. K. H. Dharan and T. F. Tan, "A hysteresis-based damage parameter for notched composite laminates subjected to cyclic loading," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 42, pp. 2204-2207, 2007/03/01 2007.
- [15] S. Giancane, F. W. Panella, and V. Dattoma, "Characterization of fatigue damage in long fiber epoxy composite laminates," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 32, pp. 46-53, 2010.
- [16] A. Belaadi, A. Bezazi, M. Bouchak, and F. Scarpa, "Tensile static and fatigue behaviour of sisal fibres," *Materials & Design*, vol. 46, pp. 76-83, 2013.
- [17] M. De Monte, E. Moosbrugger, and M. Quaresimin, "Influence of temperature and thickness on the off-axis behaviour of short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6.6–cyclic loading," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 1368-1379, 2010.
- [18] A. Shahzad and D. Isaac, "Fatigue properties of hemp and glass fiber composites," *Polymer Composites*, 2014.
- [19] K. Vallons, S. V. Lomov, and I. Verpoest, "Fatigue and post-fatigue behaviour of carbon/epoxy non-crimp fabric composites," *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 40, pp. 251-259, Mar 2009.
- [20] I. Van de Weyenberg, T. Chi Truong, B. Vangrimde, and I. Verpoest, "Improving the properties of UD flax fibre reinforced composites by applying an alkaline fibre treatment," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 37, pp. 1368-1376, 2006.